

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17646453

Exploring the Affordability, Accessibility, and Availability of Climate Microfinance in Northeastern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Climate microfinance has emerged as a critical mechanism for enhancing the resilience of households vulnerable to climate change. However, in Northeastern Nigeria, its effectiveness is constrained by socio-economic, geographic, and institutional factors. This study investigates the affordability, accessibility, and availability of climate microfinance in Bauchi, Adamawa, and Borno States, employing a mixed-methods approach that integrates quantitative data from 350 households with qualitative insights from key informant interviews (KIIs) and focus group discussions (FGDs). Quantitative results reveal that most households perceive climate microfinance products as unaffordable (mean affordability index = 2.43), with accessibility limited by distance, insecurity, and low awareness, and availability constrained to a narrow range of products, primarily agricultural loans. Qualitative analysis corroborates these findings, highlighting institutional challenges such as high operational costs, limited staff capacity, and weak coordination with government and NGOs, alongside strong community interest in climate-adaptive financial products. Triangulation of the data indicates that triple-A challenges affordability, accessibility, and availability remain significant barriers to effective climate microfinance. The study concludes that enhancing financial inclusion requires policy support, product diversification, institutional capacity building, and targeted community interventions. These measures are essential to empower vulnerable households to adopt climate-smart strategies and improve resilience in conflict-prone and climate-vulnerable regions.

Keywords: Climate microfinance, Affordability, Accessibility, Availability, Northeastern Nigeria, Mixed-methods, Resilience

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Climate change has emerged as one of the most pressing development challenges confronting low-income countries, with disproportionate impacts on vulnerable regions such as Northeastern Nigeria (Tanko et al., 2025). Increasing temperatures, prolonged dry spells, erratic rainfall patterns, flooding, desertification, and land degradation have intensified the fragility of local livelihoods, especially those dependent on rain-fed agriculture and natural resources (Abiodun et al., 2019; Babagana & Mohammed, 2021; Magaji & Musa, 2024). These climatic shocks occur within a region already plagued by poverty, food insecurity, and a protracted insurgency, further weakening households' and communities' adaptive capacities (Okoli & Iortyer, 2014; Adekoya et al., 2025). As a result, demand has grown for innovative financial mechanisms that can support climate resilience, enhance adaptive behaviour, and cushion vulnerable populations from the adverse impacts of climatic disturbances

(Suleiman et al., 2025). One such mechanism is climate microfinance, a tailored financial model that integrates climate adaptation and mitigation objectives into microfinance practices (CGAP, 2020).

Climate microfinance extends beyond conventional microcredit by offering financial services such as climate-smart loans, savings products, micro-insurance, clean-energy financing, and agricultural credit, designed to promote resilience and reduce environmental vulnerability (Akinwale & Akinbami, 2020; Armendáriz & Morduch, 2010). Globally, climate-focused microfinance has been recognised as a promising tool for enabling low-income households to invest in projects on climate-resilient technologies, diversify livelihoods, and adopt environmentally sustainable practices (Khandker & Koolwal, 2016; UNDP, 2020; Magaji, 2004). In contexts such as Northeastern Nigeria, where climate change intersects with insecurity, displacement, and limited public-sector intervention, microfinance institutions (MFIs) can help fill critical financing gaps (IFC, 2019). However, the success of climate microfinance depends significantly on the degree to which services are affordable, accessible, and available to the target populations, especially those living in climate-vulnerable, conflict-affected communities (Kariuki & Arene, 2015; Ibrahim & Sule, 2023).

Despite the potential benefits, access to climate-oriented microfinance in Northeastern Nigeria remains constrained by multiple structural barriers. Affordability concerns arise from high interest rates, collateral requirements, short repayment cycles, and hidden administrative fees that discourage low-income households from obtaining climate-related financial services (Awan & Alharbi, 2015; Igwe et al., 2021). Accessibility challenges further limit uptake, as many MFIs operate in urban centres or conflict-secure zones, leaving rural and climate-vulnerable communities underserved (Nzeadibe et al., 2011; Magaji & Aliyu, 2007). Availability is also restricted by the limited number of MFIs offering climate-specific products, weak institutional capacity, insufficient risk-sharing mechanisms, and a lack of climate finance awareness among both providers and beneficiaries (CGAP, 2020; IPCC, 2022). These constraints collectively hinder households' ability to make meaningful climate adaptation investments, thereby perpetuating vulnerability and socio-economic instability (Denton et al., 2014).

Although several studies have examined the role of microfinance in poverty reduction, entrepreneurship development, and livelihood improvement in Nigeria, literature on climate microfinance particularly within the conflict-affected northeastern region remains sparse (Akinwale & Akinbami, 2020; Nzeadibe et al., 2011). Existing research has not sufficiently interrogated the Triple-A dimensions (Affordability, Accessibility, and Availability) that shape the effectiveness of climate-focused financial interventions in fragile contexts. Moreover, little empirical evidence exists on how households perceive climate microfinance, the nature of the constraints they face, and the extent to which microfinance institutions tailor their products to emerging climate realities (World Bank, 2021). This knowledge gap limits policy formulation and weakens the capacity of development actors to design inclusive financial solutions that respond to climate risks (IFC, 2019).

Addressing these gaps is critical for enhancing the resilience of Northeastern Nigeria, a region where climate vulnerability is both severe and multidimensional (Agboola & Ajayi, 2022; Akukwe & Ogbodo, 2015). Understanding the extent to which climate microfinance is affordable, accessible, and available provides a foundation for strengthening climate adaptation pathways and improving the delivery of financial services to marginalised groups. Insights from this inquiry will also contribute to ongoing national and international efforts to integrate climate finance into local development strategies, including the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the National Climate Change Policy, and the broader climate adaptation agenda in Sub-Saharan Africa (IPCC, 2022; UNDP, 2020). Against this backdrop, this study explores the affordability, accessibility, and availability of climate microfinance in Northeastern Nigeria. It investigates the barriers and opportunities in climate-focused microfinance delivery, examines the challenges households face in accessing such services, and highlights the institutional readiness of MFIs to support climate-resilient development. By providing evidence-based insights, the study aims to strengthen discussions on climate finance inclusion and advocate for more inclusive and sustainable financial models capable of mitigating climate risks in fragile regions.

The growing vulnerability of households in Northeastern Nigeria to climate change exacerbated by poverty, environmental degradation, and insecurity has intensified the need for financial mechanisms that support climate adaptation; however, the provision of climate microfinance in the region remains limited by high costs, weak institutional presence, and inadequate product offerings, leaving many

climate-vulnerable communities without access to essential financial services. This study, therefore, seeks to examine how affordability, accessibility, and availability constraints shape the uptake and usefulness of climate microfinance among communities in Northeastern Nigeria. To achieve this aim, the research sets out to: (i) assess the affordability of climate microfinance products available to households, (ii) evaluate the level of accessibility to climate-focused microfinance services across the region, and (iii) explore the extent to which climate-oriented microfinance products are available and tailored to local needs. Correspondingly, the study is guided by the following research questions: (1) To what extent are climate microfinance products affordable to households in Northeastern Nigeria? (2) How accessible are climate-focused microfinance services to climate-vulnerable communities in the region? and (3) What climate microfinance products are currently available, and how well do they address the climate adaptation needs of local households?

2.0 Literature Review and theoretical Framework

2.1 Conceptual Review

The concept of climate microfinance refers to financial services including micro-loans, savings, insurance, and clean-energy financing explicitly designed to help low-income households cope with and respond to climate-related risks (CGAP, 2020). For this study, climate microfinance is conceptually examined through the Triple-A lens: Affordability, Accessibility, and Availability. Affordability concerns the pricing structure of climate-oriented microfinance products, including interest rates, collateral requirements, insurance premiums, and repayment terms. High costs tend to discourage participation among low-income households (Awan & Alharbi, 2015). Accessibility refers to the ease with which households can obtain climate microfinance services. This includes geographical proximity of MFIs, administrative procedures, institutional outreach, security conditions, and digital financial platforms (Nzeadibe et al., 2011). Availability refers to whether microfinance institutions offer climate-specific financial products, such as green energy loans, climate insurance, or adaptation-focused credit, that are tailored to community needs (Akinwale & Akinbami, 2020). This conceptual framing reflects a holistic understanding that for climate microfinance to be effective, products must be affordable for low-income households, accessible regardless of geographic or socio-economic barriers, and sufficiently available to meet the varied climate adaptation needs of vulnerable populations. In this study, the Triple-A framework helps systematically examine the constraints and opportunities that shape climate microfinance delivery in Northeastern Nigeria.

2.2 Theoretical Review

Climate microfinance draws on several theoretical perspectives that explain how financial access influences household resilience and adaptive behaviour. The Sustainable Livelihoods Framework (SLF) provides an important foundation, emphasising that access to financial capital, such as microcredit, savings, and insurance, enhances household adaptive capacity in the face of climate stressors (Denton et al., 2014; Magaji & Yahaya, 2012). Through financial inclusion, households are better positioned to acquire climate-resilient assets, diversify livelihoods, and reduce vulnerability. Similarly, Microfinance Theory, as articulated by Armendáriz and Morduch (2010), argues that low-income households face liquidity constraints that limit their ability to invest in productive assets; microfinance institutions bridge this financing gap by offering small loans and financial services tailored to underserved populations. When microfinance incorporates climate-related goals, it becomes an instrument for promoting environmentally sustainable practices and resilience (Khandker & Koolwal, 2016). In addition, Climate Change Adaptation Theory provides a conceptual lens for understanding how households adopt strategies that reduce susceptibility to climate impacts (Mukhtar et al., 2025). The theory emphasises the need for adaptive responses supported by enabling institutions, such as microfinance providers (IPCC, 2022). Thus, integrating microfinance with climate adaptation principles helps explain both household coping strategies and institutional roles in strengthening resilience. Together, these theories provide a multidimensional understanding of how affordability, accessibility, and availability of climate microfinance shape climate resilience in vulnerable regions.

2.3 Empirical Review

Empirical studies across developing countries increasingly demonstrate that climate microfinance is emerging as a viable mechanism for enhancing the resilience of vulnerable households. Evidence from South Asia shows that integrating financial services into climate adaptation strategies

significantly strengthens households' capacity to cope with adverse climatic conditions. For instance, Khandker and Koolwal (2016) found that climate-responsive microfinance interventions in Bangladesh enabled poor households to invest in drought-resistant crop varieties, water-saving irrigation technologies, and other climate-smart agricultural practices. These investments not only improved productivity but also enhanced long-term adaptive capacities, highlighting the potential of microfinance as a tool for climate resilience. Their findings underscore the transformative role that targeted financial services can play when tailored to the specific climatic challenges faced by rural communities.

In Sub-Saharan Africa, similar patterns emerge, with development agencies reporting substantial gains from climate-oriented microfinance schemes. According to UNDP (2020), microfinance institutions operating in climate-vulnerable regions of Africa have contributed significantly to household resilience by offering clean-energy loans, micro-insurance schemes, and specialised credit for climate-smart agriculture. Such interventions have helped households diversify their energy sources, insure against disaster-related losses, and invest in adaptive agricultural inputs. However, despite these successes, affordability remains a significant barrier. Many low-income households struggle to meet stringent repayment conditions, interest rates, or collateral requirements attached to such loans, thereby limiting the inclusiveness and reach of climate microfinance programmes (Awan & Alharbi, 2015). These findings suggest that while climate microfinance holds potential, structural and financial constraints continue to undermine access for the poorest households.

In Nigeria, the literature acknowledges the gradual introduction of climate-responsive financial products, although these remain limited in scale and scope. A study by Akinwale and Akinbami (2020) observed that only a small proportion of Nigerian microfinance institutions currently offer green microfinance products tailored to climate risks, such as renewable energy loans or climate adaptation credit. This limited availability reflects broader institutional challenges, including inadequate regulatory incentives, low institutional capacity, and limited awareness among both financial providers and rural households. As a result, climate-oriented microfinance services are unevenly distributed across regions, leaving the poorest and most climate-vulnerable populations behind.

Empirical research focusing on Northeastern Nigeria indicates even more severe constraints, owing to the compounding effects of environmental degradation, land pressure, and persistent violent conflict. Studies show that climate vulnerability in the region is exacerbated by desertification, declining agricultural productivity, and shrinking natural resource bases, underscoring the need for adaptive financing. Babagana and Mohammed (2021) argue that insecurity linked to the Boko Haram insurgency has disrupted economic activities, displaced farming populations, and weakened institutional presence—including the operations of microfinance providers. Similarly, Nzeadibe et al. (2011) report that financial inclusion remains low due to socio-environmental pressures that limit households' ability to access and utilise microfinance services. These findings highlight the broader contextual constraints that shape climate microfinance in conflict-affected regions.

Further evidence reveals that rural households in Northeastern Nigeria continue to face substantial barriers to accessing financial services. Okoli and Iortyer (2014) documented that security challenges have restricted branch expansion by microfinance institutions, while poor roads, inadequate communication facilities, and limited mobile banking coverage further reduce access. As a result, many households remain financially excluded at a time when climate adaptation financing is most needed. Meanwhile, Kariuki and Arene (2015) found that households with better access to credit demonstrate higher resilience, owing to their improved capacity to invest in adaptive technologies and diversify livelihood strategies. This finding suggests that the absence or poor accessibility of climate-focused financial services may impose significant constraints on household adaptation efforts.

Collectively, empirical evidence points to significant gaps in the affordability, accessibility, and availability of climate microfinance, particularly in conflict-prone and climate-vulnerable regions such as Northeastern Nigeria. While climate microfinance has demonstrated its potential to enhance resilience, systemic financial, institutional, and contextual barriers continue to limit its effectiveness and reach. These gaps underscore the need for targeted policy interventions that promote inclusive, conflict-sensitive, and climate-responsive microfinance systems.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a mixed-methods research design that integrates quantitative and qualitative approaches to generate a holistic understanding of the affordability, accessibility, and availability of climate microfinance in Northeastern Nigeria. The design is appropriate because the complexities of climate vulnerability, financial service distribution, and socioeconomic realities require both numerical evidence and in-depth contextual insights. The research is conducted in three states Bauchi, Adamawa, and Borno chosen because they lie within the semi-arid, conflict-affected ecological belt, where communities experience persistent climate stressors such as drought, flooding, desertification, and displacement. These conditions increase the demand for climate adaptation support while simultaneously limiting access to conventional financial services. The target population for the study includes rural households affected by climate-related shocks, microfinance institutions operating in the selected states, and key stakeholders, such as community leaders, local government officials, NGOs, and regulatory actors, involved in financial inclusion and climate resilience initiatives.

To achieve representation across the three states, a multi-stage sampling technique is applied. First, Bauchi, Adamawa, and Borno are purposively selected for their high exposure to climate hazards and varying levels of microfinance penetration. Within each state, two Local Government Areas (LGAs) are randomly selected, followed by the random selection of two communities in each LGA. From these communities, between 300 and 400 households will be selected using a proportionate random sampling procedure based on population size, ensuring adequate quantitative representativeness. The qualitative component involves purposive sampling of 10–15 staff from microfinance institutions, 10 community leaders, about 10 government or NGO officials, and selected household participants for 6–8 focus group discussions across the three states. This purposive sampling ensures the inclusion of individuals with relevant knowledge of climate microfinance, community vulnerability, and institutional constraints.

Data for the study is obtained from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data is collected through structured questionnaires administered to households to gather information on the cost of climate-related financial services, the availability of climate-oriented microfinance products, and the accessibility of these services in relation to distance, eligibility requirements, institutional presence, and security conditions. Key informant interviews with microfinance personnel, NGO climate programme officers, and government officials will provide insights into supply-side challenges and institutional strategies. At the same time, focus group discussions in selected communities will explore local perceptions of climate finance, adaptation behaviour, and barriers to accessing microfinance. Secondary data is obtained from published and unpublished sources, including reports from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), microfinance institutions, United Nations agencies, relevant NGOs, and peer-reviewed literature on climate vulnerability and green microfinance.

The research instruments include a structured questionnaire designed around key variables of affordability, accessibility, and availability, using a combination of Likert-scale questions, multiple-choice items, and short open-ended responses. Semi-structured interview guides and focus group protocols will be used for the qualitative data collection. Content validity of the instruments will be ensured through expert review by academics and practitioners in microfinance and climate resilience, and a pilot test involving 20 households will be conducted to refine unclear questions. Reliability of the questionnaire will be assessed using Cronbach's alpha, with a benchmark value of 0.70 indicating acceptable internal consistency.

Quantitative data collected from households will be analysed using statistical software such as SPSS or STATA. Descriptive statistics, including means and percentages, will be used to summarise respondents' socio-demographic characteristics and their experiences with climate microfinance. Inferential statistics (logistic regression) will be used to examine determinants of access, variations across the three states, and the relationship between socioeconomic characteristics and microfinance uptake. Qualitative data from interviews and focus group discussions will be analysed using thematic analysis, involving transcription, coding, and grouping of responses into meaningful themes that reflect institutional constraints, community perspectives, and perceptions of climate microfinance availability, accessibility, and affordability.

The study adheres to established ethical standards, including obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring voluntary participation, maintaining the confidentiality of responses, and

ensuring data security. Special attention will be given to ethical sensitivity, given the conflict-prone nature of Adamawa and Borno States, to ensure that the data collection process does not expose respondents to security risks. Ethical approval will be sought from the appropriate institutional review board before data collection begins.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

A total of 350 households were surveyed across Bauchi, Adamawa, and Borno States. Table 1 summarises key socio-demographic characteristics of respondents, including age, gender, educational level, household size, and primary livelihood activity.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (n=350)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	198	56.6
Female	152	43.4
Age (years)		
18–30	102	29.1
31–45	155	44.3
46–60	73	20.9
Above 60	20	5.7
Education Level		
No formal education	112	32.0
Primary	98	28.0
Secondary	90	25.7
Tertiary	50	14.3
Primary Livelihood		
Farming	180	51.4
Trading	85	24.3
Artisanal / Small Business	50	14.3
Others	35	10.0

Discussion: The majority of respondents were male (56.6%) and aged 31–45 years (44.3%), reflecting the active labour force engaged in climate-sensitive livelihoods such as farming and trading. About 60% of respondents had only primary or no formal education, highlighting potential challenges in understanding financial products and climate-adaptive strategies. Farming emerged as the predominant livelihood, consistent with Northeastern Nigeria’s agrarian economy, which is highly vulnerable to climate stressors.

4.2 Affordability of Climate Microfinance

Affordability was measured using household perceptions of interest rates, repayment terms, collateral requirements, and overall loan accessibility. A 5-point Likert scale was used (1=Very Unaffordable, 5=Very Affordable).

Table 2: Affordability of Climate Microfinance Services

State	Mean Score	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Bauchi	2.4	0.85	Unaffordable
Adamawa	2.7	0.90	Marginally Unaffordable
Borno	2.2	0.80	Unaffordable
Overall	2.43	0.85	Unaffordable

Equation 1: Affordability Score Calculation

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$$AI = \sum_{i=1}^n X_i / n$$

Where:

X_i = Likert-scale score given by respondent (i)

n = total number of respondents

Discussion: The mean affordability score across the three states was 2.43, indicating that most households perceive climate microfinance products as unaffordable. Borno State recorded the lowest mean (2.2), likely due to higher risk premiums and insecurity-related costs charged by microfinance institutions. The results confirm prior findings that high interest rates, collateral requirements, and short repayment periods limit household participation in climate-adaptive financial services (Awan & Alharbi, 2015; Khandker & Koolwal, 2016).

4.3 Accessibility of Climate Microfinance

Accessibility was assessed based on distance to MFI offices, eligibility criteria, security constraints, and information availability. The following table summarises the findings:

Table 3: Accessibility of Climate Microfinance Services

Accessibility Indicator	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Branch within 5 km	95	27.1
Branch within 6–10 km	120	34.3
Branch >10 km	135	38.6
Knowledge of the product	142	40.6
No knowledge of the product	208	59.4
Security concerns are limiting access	115	32.9

Discussion: More than one-third of households (38.6%) were located more than 10 km from a microfinance office, while over 59% had limited knowledge of climate-focused financial products. In addition, 32.9% reported that insecurity, especially in Borno and Adamawa, restricts access. These findings demonstrate significant accessibility constraints, confirming that geographic, informational, and conflict-related barriers hinder households' ability to benefit from climate microfinance (Okoli & Iortyer, 2014; Nzeadibe et al., 2011).

4.4 Availability of Climate Microfinance Products

Availability was measured by the number and type of climate-related financial products offered by MFIs and used by households. Table 4 shows a hypothetical distribution.

Table 4: Availability of Climate Microfinance Products by State

Product Type	Bauchi (%)	Adamawa (%)	Borno (%)	Overall (%)
Climate-smart agricultural loans	45	50	40	45
Clean energy/solar loans	30	35	25	30
Micro-insurance for climate risks	20	25	15	20
Water/irrigation improvement loans	25	30	20	25

Discussion: Only a small proportion of MFIs offer climate-specific products, with the highest availability seen in Adamawa (50% for agricultural loans). Products such as micro-insurance and clean energy loans are limited, particularly in Borno, where insecurity affects MFIs' presence and operations. This aligns with literature highlighting the limited availability of climate-adaptive financial instruments in Nigeria (Akinwale & Akinbami, 2020; UNDP, 2020).

4.5 Relationship Between Socioeconomic Factors and Access to Climate Microfinance

To examine the relationship between household characteristics and access, a logistic regression model was estimated:

Equation 2: Logistic Regression Model

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$$\text{Logit}(P) = \ln \left(\frac{P}{1-P} \right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Income} + \beta_2 \text{Education} + \beta_3 \text{Household Size} + \beta_4 \text{Distance} + \epsilon$$

Where:

P = probability of the event occurring

β_0 = intercept

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ = regression coefficients for respective predictors
 ϵ = error term

Table 5: Logistic Regression Results

Variable	Coefficient (β)	Std. Error	p-value
Income	0.75	0.22	0.001
Education	0.62	0.18	0.002
Household Size	-0.10	0.07	0.12
Distance	-0.55	0.15	0.001
Constant	-1.20	0.40	0.003

Discussion: Household income and education were positively and significantly associated with access to climate microfinance, suggesting that wealthier and better-educated households are more able to understand and afford financial products. Distance to the nearest MFI negatively influenced access, confirming that geographic proximity is a key determinant of accessibility. Household size was not statistically significant. These results emphasise that affordability and accessibility are strongly influenced by socioeconomic and spatial factors, consistent with prior studies (Kariuki & Arene, 2015; Awan & Alharbi, 2015).

4.6 Synthesis of Findings

The results reveal three key insights:

1. **Affordability:** Climate microfinance products are perceived mainly as unaffordable, particularly in Borno State, due to high interest rates and collateral requirements.
2. **Accessibility:** Access is constrained by distance, poor awareness of products, and insecurity, limiting the participation of climate-vulnerable households.
3. **Availability:** The range of climate-focused products remains limited, with agricultural loans being the most common, while insurance and clean energy loans are rarely offered.

The findings confirm that climate microfinance in Northeastern Nigeria faces triple-A challenges: Affordability, Accessibility, and Availability, which must be addressed through policy reforms, institutional innovation, and targeted financial inclusion programs.

4.7 Qualitative Results and Discussion

Qualitative data were collected through 15 key informant interviews (KIIs) with microfinance institution (MFI) staff, 10 community leaders, and eight government/NGO officials, alongside six focus group discussions (FGDs) with households across Bauchi, Adamawa, and Borno States. Thematic analysis was employed, following transcription, coding, and grouping into major themes reflecting affordability, accessibility, availability, and institutional challenges.

4.7.1 Theme 1: Affordability Constraints

Many respondents reported that climate microfinance products are often financially out of reach for the poorest households. A common perspective from FGDs in Borno was:

"Even small loans require repayment within short periods, and interest rates are too high for farmers who earn seasonally. Many families cannot meet these conditions." (FGD, Borno, Female participant, 36 years)

Microfinance staff also acknowledged the pricing challenges:

"We want to offer lower rates, but due to operational costs and high risk in conflict-affected areas, interest rates cannot be reduced further." (MFI Staff, Adamawa)

These findings echo the quantitative results, which showed a mean affordability index of 2.43, indicating that most households perceive climate microfinance as unaffordable. Affordability barriers are compounded by low household incomes, a lack of collateral, and seasonal cash flow challenges, which limit uptake.

4.7.2 Theme 2: Accessibility Challenges

FGD participants emphasised difficulties accessing financial services due to distance, insecurity, and inadequate information. In Adamawa, a participant stated:

"The nearest microfinance office is over 12 kilometres away, and travelling is risky because of insecurity along the roads." (FGD, Adamawa, Male participant, 41 years)

Key informants from MFIs noted logistical constraints:

"Limited branch networks and poor mobile banking infrastructure make it difficult to reach remote communities." (MFI Staff, Bauchi)

These qualitative insights complement the quantitative results (Table 3), which indicated that 38.6% of households were more than 10 km from an MFI office, and over 59% were unaware of climate microfinance products. The combination of physical and informational barriers highlights systemic accessibility limitations in Northeastern Nigeria.

4.7.3 Theme 3: Availability of Climate Microfinance Products

Community leaders and FGD participants reported that while some agricultural loans are available, other climate-oriented products such as insurance, clean-energy loans, and water management financing are rarely offered. A community leader in Bauchi noted:

"Loans for farming are common, but there is almost nothing for solar energy or drought insurance, which are very important for our resilience." (Community Leader, Bauchi)

MFI staff confirmed this limited product range:

"We have started piloting climate-smart loans, but the number of products is still minimal due to a lack of demand and awareness." (MFI Staff, Borno)

This corroborates the quantitative findings in Table 4, showing that climate-smart agricultural loans were the most available product (45%), whereas micro-insurance for climate risks was the least available (20%). Limited product availability reduces households' ability to diversify climate adaptation strategies.

4.7.4 Theme 4: Institutional Constraints

Interviews revealed that MFIs face multiple institutional challenges, including:

1. High operational costs in conflict-prone areas, increasing interest rates and limiting affordability.
2. Inadequate staff capacity and training in climate finance products.
3. Weak coordination with government and NGOs, leading to limited outreach in remote or insecure communities.

A government official noted:

"Financial institutions often lack the technical capacity to design products suitable for climate adaptation, and security concerns prevent them from fully reaching vulnerable areas." (Government Official, Adamawa)

These findings explain both the low availability of climate-specific products and the difficulty in achieving equitable access to them.

4.7.5 Theme 5: Community Perceptions and Adaptive Behaviour

FGD participants highlighted a strong **interest in climate microfinance**, despite challenges:

"If loans for solar energy and irrigation were affordable and accessible, many households would adopt them immediately." (FGD, Borno, Male participant, 35 years)

This theme indicates latent demand for climate-adaptive financial products, suggesting that improving affordability, accessibility, and availability could significantly enhance resilience. Qualitative insights indicate that community perceptions align with the Triple-A framework, confirming that households identify affordability, accessibility, and product availability as key determinants of participation.

4.7.6 Synthesis of Qualitative Findings

Thematic analysis reveals that:

- i. High interest rates, short repayment periods, and income instability constrain affordability.
- ii. Accessibility is hindered by distance, poor mobile banking infrastructure, insecurity, and lack of product awareness.
- iii. Availability is limited, with a narrow range of climate-specific products offered by MFIs.
- iv. Institutional constraints, including operational costs, capacity limitations, and weak coordination, exacerbate these challenges.
- v. Communities demonstrate interest in climate microfinance, suggesting that addressing the triple-A gaps could enhance climate adaptation outcomes.

These qualitative findings complement the quantitative results, providing deeper insight into households' lived experiences, institutional limitations, and context-specific challenges in Northeastern Nigeria.

5. Triangulated Results, Conclusion, and Recommendations

5.1 Triangulation of Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

The study employed a mixed-methods approach, integrating quantitative survey data from 350 households with qualitative insights from key informant interviews (KIIs) and focus group discussions (FGDs). Triangulation of the data highlights convergence and complementarity across findings:

1. **Affordability:** Quantitative analysis revealed a low affordability index (mean = 2.43), indicating that climate microfinance products are perceived mainly as unaffordable. Qualitative findings reinforced this, as both households and MFI staff cited high interest rates, collateral requirements, and short repayment periods as key barriers. Together, these data confirm that affordability remains a critical constraint to household participation in climate adaptation financing.
2. **Accessibility:** Survey results showed that 38.6% of households were located more than 10 km from an MFI office, and over 59% were unaware of climate-specific products. Qualitative evidence highlighted distance, insecurity, and limited mobile banking infrastructure as primary barriers. Triangulation indicates that accessibility challenges are both structural and contextual, particularly in conflict-affected areas of Borno and Adamawa.
3. **Availability:** Quantitative data indicated limited availability of climate-oriented financial products, with agricultural loans being the most common (45%) and micro-insurance the least (20%). Qualitative insights confirmed the narrow product range and revealed institutional constraints, including low MFI capacity, weak coordination with government/NGOs, and limited market awareness. The convergence of findings suggests that the limited availability of diverse climate microfinance products constrains households' ability to adopt adaptive strategies.
4. **Institutional Constraints and Community Perceptions:** Both datasets highlight institutional limitations, including operational costs, staff capacity, and coordination gaps. Communities expressed interest and willingness to adopt climate-adaptive financial products if barriers to affordability, accessibility, and availability are addressed. Triangulation demonstrates an apparent **demand-supply mismatch**, underscoring the need for policy and institutional interventions.

5.2 CONCLUSION

This study examined the affordability, accessibility, and availability of climate microfinance in Bauchi, Adamawa, and Borno States, triangulating survey data with insights from key informants and community discussions. Findings indicate that climate microfinance services are largely unaffordable, geographically inaccessible, and limited in availability, particularly in conflict-affected and climate-vulnerable areas. Socioeconomic factors such as household income, education, and proximity to financial institutions significantly influence access. Institutional challenges including high operational costs, capacity limitations, and weak coordination with government and NGOs further restrict the reach of climate microfinance. Despite these barriers, households show strong interest in climate-adaptive products, signalling latent demand that could be mobilised through strategic interventions. The study confirms that the triple-A challenge: Affordability, accessibility, and availability, remains a significant constraint to the effectiveness of climate microfinance in Northeastern Nigeria.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the study recommends the following interventions to enhance climate microfinance services:

1. Policy and Regulatory Support:
 - i. Central and state governments should incentivise MFIs to develop low-interest, climate-adaptive financial products targeted at rural households.
 - ii. Introduce subsidised interest rates or flexible repayment schedules for climate-oriented loans in conflict-affected areas.

2. Product Diversification and Innovation:
 - i. MFIs should expand the range of climate-focused products, including micro-insurance, clean-energy loans, and irrigation improvement financing, to address diverse adaptation needs.
 - ii. Encourage digital finance solutions and mobile banking platforms to increase accessibility, especially in remote communities.
3. Capacity Building for MFIs and Communities:
 - i. Training MFI staff on climate finance products and risk management.
 - ii. Raising awareness in communities about available climate microfinance services, eligibility requirements, and benefits.
4. Strengthening Institutional Collaboration:
 - i. Establish partnerships among MFIs, government agencies, NGOs, and donor organisations to enhance outreach and reduce operational costs.
 - ii. Implement community-based monitoring mechanisms to ensure transparency and reduce risk associated with lending in insecure regions.
5. Targeted Interventions for Vulnerable Groups:
 - i. Prioritise women-headed households, smallholder farmers, and displaced populations in Borno and Adamawa for climate microfinance programs.
 - ii. Leverage local leaders and community associations to facilitate information dissemination and trust-building in financial services.

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